
Automatic Constraint Policy Optimization based on Continuous Constraint Interpolation Framework for Offline Reinforcement Learning

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Abstract

Offline Reinforcement Learning (RL) relies on policy constraints to mitigate extrapolation error, where both the constraint form and constraint strength critically shape performance. However, most existing methods commit to a single constraint family: weighted behavior cloning, density regularization, or support constraints, without a unified principle that explains their connections or trade-offs. In this work, we propose Continuous Constraint Interpolation (CCI), a unified optimization framework in which these three constraint families arise as special cases along a common constraint spectrum. The CCI framework introduces a single interpolation parameter that enables smooth transitions and principled combinations across constraint types. Building on CCI, we develop Automatic Constraint Policy Optimization (ACPO), a practical primal–dual algorithm that adapts the interpolation parameter via a Lagrangian dual update. Moreover, we establish a maximum-entropy performance difference lemma and derive performance lower bounds for both the closed-form optimal policy and its parametric projection. Experiments on D4RL and NeoRL2 demonstrate robust gains across diverse domains, achieving state-of-the-art performance overall.

1. Introduction

RL tackles sequential decision-making through online interaction with an environment (Han et al., 2024). However, in many real-world applications, such interaction can be expensive, risky, or even infeasible. To address this limitation, offline RL, which aims to learn effective policies from pre-collected datasets without further interaction, has received growing attention in recent years. Yet, removing interac-

tion also introduces fundamental challenges. In particular, extrapolation error (Fujimoto et al., 2019) arises when Q -function estimates are queried on out-of-distribution (OOD) actions that are poorly supported by the dataset. Such errors can be amplified by bootstrapping, leading to severe overestimation and, ultimately, degraded performance and instability (Levine et al., 2020; Kumar et al., 2020; Han et al., 2025d; Kim et al., 2025).

A dominant paradigm of offline RL methods mitigates extrapolation error by constraining the learned policy to stay close to the behavior policy that generated the dataset. In practice, however, the behavior policy is often unknown: offline data may come from random exploration, mixtures of multiple tasks, heterogeneous sources, or logged trajectories collected during online RL training (Chen et al., 2022; Lyu et al., 2022). Under such ambiguity, selecting an appropriate form and strength of policy constraint becomes crucial.

From a high-level perspective, mainstream policy-constrained approaches in offline RL can be organized into three categories along a common constraint spectrum: weighted behavior cloning (wBC), density regularization, and support constraints. wBC remains fundamentally imitative and typically reduces to weighted supervised learning on the dataset (Chen et al., 2020; Florence et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2022; Fujimoto & Gu, 2021). Density regularization allows controlled distributional deviation from the behavior policy. In particular, KL-based density regularization is widely used to limit the magnitude of distributional shift from the behavior distribution (Peters & Schaal, 2007; Peng et al., 2019; Nair et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020). Support constraints, instead of matching the behavior distribution, encourage the learned policy to select actions within the support of the behavior policy (Kumar et al., 2019; Han et al., 2025c; Wu et al., 2022; Mao et al., 2023). However, overly conservative constraints can stabilize policy evaluation but undermine the core promise of offline RL—policy improvement beyond the dataset; while overly weak constraints fail to meaningfully restrict policy improvement, tending to select OOD actions and inducing large value misestimation that misguides optimization (Wu et al., 2025; Han et al., 2025a).

To cope with this trade-off, several recent works (Zhou et al.,

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2022; Luo et al., 2025; Han et al., 2025c) explore adaptive constraint schemes. However, existing approaches typically adapt within a single constraint paradigm, and a unified view that simultaneously covers and connects wBC, KL-based density regularization, and support constraints remains missing. As a result, practitioners still need to manually choose the constraint form and then tune its strength, which can be nontrivial across datasets and tasks.

In this paper, we develop a unified optimization framework, the *Continuous Constraint Interpolation (CCI)* framework, and show that the above three constraint families arise as special cases. The CCI framework exposes a single interpolation parameter that enables smooth transitions and principled combinations among wBC, KL-based density regularization, and support constraints for policy improvement. Building on the CCI framework, we propose *Automatic Constraint Policy Optimization (ACPO)*, a practical offline RL algorithm that optimizes the interpolation parameter via a Lagrangian dual update, thereby eliminating the need to manually select fixed constraint forms and strengths. Intuitively, the interpolation parameter acts as a constraint “dial” that automatically adapts the constraints regime during training.

Our key contributions can be summarized as follows:

- **Unified CCI Framework.** We propose CCI, a unified optimization framework that bridges three major policy-constraint families: wBC, KL-based density regularization, and support constraints, and enables smooth transitions as well as principled combinations across constraint regimes.
- **Practical ACPO Algorithm.** Building on CCI, we develop ACPO, a practical primal–dual algorithm that automatically adapts the interpolation parameter through a Lagrangian dual update. We further establish a maximum-entropy performance difference lemma and derive performance lower bounds for both the optimal policy and its practical parametric projection.
- **Empirical Evaluation.** We perform extensive comparisons and ablations on the standard D4RL and the recent NeoRL2 benchmarks, showing that ACPO achieves consistent improvements across diverse domains and tasks.

2. Related Works

In offline RL, policy constraints are not the only mechanism for mitigating extrapolation error induced by OOD actions. Beyond policy constraints, prior work has explored conservative value estimation (Kumar et al., 2020; Peng et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2024), ensemble-based uncertainty-aware methods (An et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2025; Bai et al., 2022),

and DIstribution Correction Estimation (DICE) algorithms (Nachum et al., 2019; Lee et al., 2021; Mao et al., 2024). To highlight the advantages of our framework and algorithm, we focus the remainder of this section on policy-constrained offline RL and organize representative methods into three categories: wBC, density regularization, and support constraints.

wBC methods either cast policy learning as (weighted) supervised imitation on the dataset, or incorporate an explicit BC regularizer into the policy improvement objective. BAIL (Chen et al., 2020) learns a value function and imitates only actions selected as high-quality under the learned value. IBC (Florence et al., 2022) improves expressiveness via implicit energy-based policies, avoiding the limitations of explicit regression-based models. DWBC (Xu et al., 2022) trains a discriminator to estimate expert-likeness and uses it to reweight the BC loss. In contrast, TD3+BC (Fujimoto & Gu, 2021) augments value-based policy improvement with a BC term, mitigating distributional drift during policy improvement.

Density regularization methods allow controlled deviation from the behavior policy by penalizing distributional shift at the policy level. The most common choice is KL-based regularization (Peters & Schaal, 2007; Peng et al., 2019; Nair et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020; Kostrikov et al., 2021b), due to its elegant and tractable policy improvement objective, which keeps policy updates via stable in-sample learning. For completeness, we also review density regularization choices beyond KL divergence, including MMD-based constraints for sample-based distribution matching (Wu et al., 2020), Fisher divergence (Kostrikov et al., 2021a), and Wasserstein distance regularization (Omura et al., 2025; Asadulaev et al., 2024).

Support constraint methods perform policy improvement with the policy constrained within the support of the behavior policy. EMaQ (Ghasemipour et al., 2021) samples multiple candidate actions from behavior policy and performs backups over these in-support proposals. STR (Mao et al., 2023) combines trust-region policy optimization with an explicit support constraint via Importance Sampling (IS), ensuring that each update remains within the behavior support. SPOT (Wu et al., 2022) trains a VAE-based estimator to model the behavior support and introduces a simple plugin regularization term that keeps policy improvement within the estimated support.

Overall, most existing approaches operate within a single policy-constraint paradigm. A unified optimization view that bridges all three families under one framework—enabling smooth transitions, flexible combinations, and automatic adaptation across constraint regimes—remains missing. We therefore propose the CCI framework and derive a practical algorithm, ACPO.

3. Preliminaries

3.1. Maximum Entropy RL

Conventionally, an RL problem is defined as a Markov Decision Process (MDP) (Sutton & Barto, 2018), specified by a tuple $\mathcal{M} = \langle \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{T}, r, \gamma \rangle$, where \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{A} denote the state and action spaces, \mathcal{T} represents the transition function, r is the reward function, and $\gamma \in [0, 1)$ denotes the discount factor. The performance difference lemma (Kakade & Langford, 2002) in the standard RL setting gives

$$\eta(\pi') - \eta(\pi) = \frac{1}{1 - \gamma} \sum_s d_{\pi'}(s) \sum_a \pi'(a|s) A^\pi(s, a), \quad (1)$$

where $\eta(\pi) = \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim \pi} [\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t r(s_t, a_t)]$, and $\mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim \pi} [\dots]$ denotes the expectation under the trajectory τ induced by the interconnection of π and the environment. $d_{\pi'}(s)$ denotes the discounted state visitation distribution under π' , and $A^\pi(s, a) = Q^\pi(s, a) - V^\pi(s)$ is the advantage function.

In the maximum-entropy setting (Haarnoja et al., 2017; Asadi & Littman, 2017; Haarnoja et al., 2018; Xiao et al., 2019), the objective augments rewards with an entropy term:

$$\mathcal{J}(\pi) = \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim \pi} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t \left(r(s_t, a_t) - \alpha \log \pi(a_t|s_t) \right) \right], \quad (2)$$

where $\alpha > 0$ is the temperature parameter and $\mathcal{H}(s, \pi) = \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} [-\log \pi(a|s)]$. The maximum-entropy value function is defined as $V^\pi(s) = \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} [Q^\pi(s, a) - \alpha \log \pi(a|s)]$. The soft Q -function is $Q^\pi(s, a) = r(s, a) + \gamma \mathbb{E}_{s' \sim \mathcal{T}(\cdot|s, a)} [V^\pi(s')]$. As $\alpha \rightarrow 0$, maximum entropy RL recovers the standard RL.

3.2. wBC Methods

The generalized wBC objective can be defined as follows,

$$\max_{\pi} \mathcal{J}^{\text{wBC}}(\pi) = \mathbb{E}_{(s, a) \sim \mathcal{D}} [w^{\text{bc}}(s, a) \log \pi(a|s)], \quad (3)$$

where $w^{\text{bc}} : \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ denotes a weight function. For example, $w^{\text{bc}}(s, a) = 1$ corresponds the vanilla BC method, while more sophisticated choices are used in, e.g., (Xu et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2020).

3.3. KL-based Density Regularization Methods

KL-based density regularization methods can be summarized by the following policy optimization problem (Mao et al., 2023):

$$\begin{aligned} \pi^*(a|s) &= \arg \max_{\pi} \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} [A^{\pi_{\text{pe}}}(s, a)], \\ \text{s.t. } D_{KL}[\pi(\cdot|s) || \pi_{\text{base}}(\cdot|s)] &\leq \epsilon, \\ \int_a \pi(a|s) da &= 1, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where π_{base} denotes a reference (sampling) policy and π_{pe} denotes the evaluation policy. The optimization problem Eq. (4) admits a parametric solution, which can be written as

$$\max_{\pi} \mathcal{J}^{\text{KL}}(\pi) = \mathbb{E}_{s \sim \mathcal{D}, a \sim \pi_{\text{base}}} [w^{\text{kl}}(s, a) \log \pi(a|s)], \quad (5)$$

where $w^{\text{kl}}(s, a) = \exp\left(\frac{A^{\pi_{\text{pe}}}(s, a)}{\alpha}\right)$. Different choices of π_{base} and π_{pe} give rise to different algorithmic instantiations (Nair et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020; Siegel et al., 2020), while sharing the same KL-regularized principle.

3.4. Support Constraint Methods

The support constraint requires the learned policy to assign positive density only on actions supported by the behavior policy, e.g., $\pi_{\beta}(a|s) = 0 \Rightarrow \pi(a|s) = 0$.

InAC (Xiao et al., 2023) introduces an in-sample softmax operator and implements support-constrained policy improvement by sampling actions from the dataset:

$$\max_{\pi} \mathcal{J}^{\text{Supp}}(\pi) = \mathbb{E}_{(s, a) \sim \mathcal{D}} [w^{\text{supp}}(s, a) \log \pi(a|s)], \quad (6)$$

where $w^{\text{supp}}(s, a) = \exp\left(\frac{A^{\pi}(s, a)}{\alpha} - \log \pi_{\beta}(a|s)\right)$.

Because $\exp(-\log \pi_{\beta}(a|s)) = \pi_{\beta}(a|s)^{-1}$, the above is equivalent to $\pi(a|s) = 0$ when $\pi_{\beta}(a|s) = 0$ and otherwise $\pi(a|s) \propto \exp(A^{\pi}(s, a)/\alpha)$ ¹. The learned policy π is not skewed by the action probabilities in π_{β} ; it just has the same support (Xiao et al., 2023).

4. Unified Policy Constraints for Offline RL

4.1. Continuous Constraint Interpolation Framework

The CCI framework provides a unified optimization view of three policy-constraint families: wBC, KL-based density regularization, and support constraints. It treats them as instances along a common constraint spectrum, and enables smooth switching and principled combinations via a single continuous interpolation parameter.

Consider the following constrained maximum-entropy policy optimization problem,

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\pi} \mathbb{E}_{s \sim \mathcal{D}, a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} [Q(s, a) - \alpha \log \pi(a|s)], \\ \text{s.t. } \mathbb{E}_{s \sim \mathcal{D}, a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} [\log \pi_{\beta}(a|s)] \geq \epsilon, \\ \int \pi(a|s) da = 1, \forall s. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

We do not impose per-state hard constraints, which would introduce an impractical (potentially infinite) number of constraints (Wu et al., 2022). Instead, we enforce the constraint on average over dataset states, yielding a single scalar constraint.

¹InAC defines $0 \cdot \infty = 0$.

λ	Constraint	$w_\lambda(s, a)$
$\lambda = 0$	Support Constraint	$\exp\left(\frac{A(s,a)}{\alpha} - \log \pi_\beta(a s)\right)$.
$0 < \lambda < \alpha$	Support-to-Density Constraint	$\exp\left(\frac{A(s,a)}{\alpha} - \frac{\alpha-\lambda}{\alpha} \log \pi_\beta(a s)\right)$.
$\lambda = \alpha$	KL-based Density Constraint	$\exp\left(\frac{A(s,a)}{\alpha}\right)$.
$\lambda > \alpha$	Density-to-wBC Constraint	$\exp\left(\frac{A(s,a)}{\alpha} + \frac{\lambda-\alpha}{\alpha} \log \pi_\beta(a s)\right)$.
$\lambda \gg \alpha + A(s, a)(\log \pi_\beta(a s))^{-1}$	Practical wBC Constraint	$\approx \exp\left(\frac{\lambda-\alpha}{\alpha} \log \pi_\beta(a s)\right)$.

 Table 1. Constraint spectrum induced by the interpolation parameter λ in the CCI framework.

Solving the above problem Eq. (7) via the Lagrangian,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(\pi, \lambda, \nu) = & \mathbb{E}_{s \sim \mathcal{D}, a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} [Q(s, a) - \alpha \log \pi(a|s)] \\ & + \lambda \left(\mathbb{E}_{s \sim \mathcal{D}, a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} [\log \pi_\beta(a|s)] - \epsilon \right) \\ & + \mathbb{E}_{s \sim \mathcal{D}} \left[\nu(s) \left(\int \pi(a|s) da - 1 \right) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

we obtain the following closed-form optimal policy:

$$\pi_\lambda^*(a|s) = \exp\left(\frac{Q(s, a) - Z_\lambda(s)}{\alpha}\right) \pi_\beta(a|s)^{\lambda/\alpha}. \quad (9)$$

where $\lambda \geq 0$ denotes the dual variable, and $Z_\lambda(s) = \alpha \log \int \exp(Q(s, a)/\alpha) \pi_\beta(a|s)^{\lambda/\alpha} da$ is the log-normalizer.

Then, we project the non-parametric optimal policy π_λ^* into the parametric space π_θ by minimizing the reverse KL divergence,

$$\pi_\theta(a|s) = \arg \min_{\pi_\theta} \mathbb{E}_{s \sim \mathcal{D}} [D_{\text{KL}}[\pi_\lambda^*(\cdot|s) || \pi_\theta(\cdot|s)]]. \quad (10)$$

This yields the following policy improvement objective under CCI:

$$\max_{\theta} \mathcal{J}^{\text{CCI}}(\theta; \lambda) = \mathbb{E}_{(s,a) \sim \mathcal{D}} [w_\lambda(s, a) \log \pi_\theta(a|s)], \quad (11)$$

where $w_\lambda(s, a) = \exp\left(\frac{A(s,a)}{\alpha} + \frac{\lambda-\alpha}{\alpha} \log \pi_\beta(a|s)\right)$.

Based on the policy improvement objective Eq. (11), varying λ enables continuous interpolation of the constraint spectrum, allowing smooth transitions and flexible combinations, shown in Tab. 1.

We note that the practical wBC regime corresponds to choosing $\lambda \gg \alpha + A(s, a)(\log \pi_\beta(a|s))^{-1}$. Under the maximum-entropy setting, assume rewards are bounded by $|r(s, a)| \leq R_{\max}$ and we stabilize training by clipping log-probabilities for any stochastic policy as $\log \pi(a|s) \in [\ell_{\min}, \ell_{\max}]$. Let

$$C_{\max} \triangleq \max\{|\ell_{\min}|, |\ell_{\max}|\} \Rightarrow |-\alpha \log \pi(a|s)| \leq \alpha C_{\max}.$$

Then one can obtain a uniform advantage bound $|A^\pi(s, a)| \leq \frac{2(R_{\max} + \alpha C_{\max})}{1-\gamma}$ and consequently, with

$C_{\min}^\beta \triangleq \min |\log \pi_\beta(a|s)|$ and a small constant $\delta > 0$ to avoid division by zero,

$$\left| \frac{A(s, a)}{\log \pi_\beta(a|s)} \right| \leq \frac{2(R_{\max} + \alpha C_{\max})}{(1-\gamma)(C_{\min}^\beta + \delta)}. \quad (12)$$

Therefore, a sufficient condition for the practical wBC constraint is

$$\lambda \gg \alpha + \frac{2(R_{\max} + \alpha C_{\max})}{(1-\gamma)(C_{\min}^\beta + \delta)}. \quad (13)$$

The derivations for this subsection are provided in Appendix A.

4.2. Automatic Constraint Policy Optimization

Building on the CCI framework, we propose ACPO, a practical primal–dual method that automatically tunes the constraint form and strength parameter λ .

For a fixed Q -function, the objective in Eq. (7) is maximizing a concave objective in π , and the inequality constraint and normalization constraints are affine. Therefore, under standard regularity assumptions (ensuring \mathcal{L} is well-defined) and Slater’s condition, strong duality holds, and the primal problem is equivalent to the dual form,

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\lambda} \max_{\pi_\theta \in \Delta} \mathcal{L}(\pi_\theta, \lambda), \\ \text{s.t. } \lambda \geq 0, \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where Δ denotes the set of valid policies.

ACPO alternates between (i) updating π_θ to maximize the CCI objective Eq. (11) for a fixed λ , and (ii) performing a projected gradient descent step on λ to enforce the constraint:

$$\lambda \leftarrow \left[\lambda - \eta_\lambda \left(\mathbb{E}_{s \sim \mathcal{D}, a \sim \pi_\theta} [\log \pi_\beta(a|s)] - \epsilon \right) \right]_+. \quad (15)$$

This update increases λ when the constraint is violated, and decreases it when the constraint is overly conservative. By updating λ online via Eq. (15), ACPO automatically adapts the effective constraint regime to the dataset.

For policy evaluation, we adopt standard maximum-entropy critic updates with Clipped Double Q-Learning (Fujimoto

et al., 2018):

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_V(\psi) &= \mathbb{E}_{s \sim \mathcal{D}, a \sim \pi_\theta(\cdot|s)} \left[\frac{1}{2} (V_\psi(s) - Y_V(s, a))^2 \right], \\ Y_V(s, a) &\triangleq \min_{i \in \{1, 2\}} Q_{\phi_i}(s, a) - \alpha \log \pi_\theta(a|s). \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_Q(\phi_i) = \mathbb{E}_{(s, a, r, s') \sim \mathcal{D}} \left[\frac{1}{2} (r + \gamma V_\psi(s') - Q_{\phi_i}(s, a))^2 \right]. \quad (17)$$

Following common practice in offline RL (Xiao et al., 2023; Han et al., 2025c), we fit the behavior policy π_β on the dataset via maximum likelihood:

$$\mathcal{L}(\pi_\beta) = \mathbb{E}_{(s, a) \sim \mathcal{D}} [-\log \pi_\beta(a|s)]. \quad (18)$$

Integrating policy improvement, policy evaluation, and dual optimization, the complete ACPO algorithm is summarized in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 ACPO

Input: Dataset $\mathcal{D} = \{(s, a, r, s')\}$.

Parameters: Q -networks $Q_{\phi_{1,2}}$, target Q -networks $Q_{\phi'_{1,2}}$, value network V_ψ , policy network π_θ , behavior policy network π_β .

- 1: // **Pre-train behavior policy for N_β steps.**
 - 2: **for** $t = 1$ to N_β **do**
 - 3: Optimize π_β by Eq. (18).
 - 4: **end for**
 - 5: // **Policy evaluation, improvement, and dual update.**
 - 6: **for** each gradient step **do**
 - 7: Sample $(s, a, r, s') \sim \mathcal{D}$.
 - 8: Optimize V_ψ by Eq. (16).
 - 9: Optimize Q_{ϕ_i} by Eq. (17).
 - 10: Update λ by Eq. (15).
 - 11: Optimize π_θ by Eq. (11).
 - 12: Soft-update target networks $\phi' \leftarrow (1 - \tau)\phi' + \tau\phi$.
 - 13: **end for**
 - 14: **return** Policy π_θ .
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4.3. Theoretical Analysis

The CCI framework admits a closed-form optimizer π_λ^* parameterized by the dual variable λ . We first formalize how λ controls conservatism by studying the constraint $\mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi_\lambda^*(\cdot|s)} [\log \pi_\beta(a|s)]$. We then derive a maximum-entropy performance difference lemma and establish performance lower bounds for both the optimal policy π_λ^* and its parametric projection π_θ .

Proposition 4.1. Fix any state s and temperature $\alpha > 0$. Let $\pi_\lambda^*(\cdot|s)$ denote the closed-form optimizer in Eq. (9) for

a given $\lambda \geq 0$. Define

$$g_s(\lambda) := \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi_\lambda^*(\cdot|s)} [\log \pi_\beta(a|s)]. \quad (19)$$

Then $g_s(\lambda)$ is monotone non-decreasing in λ , and

$$\frac{d}{d\lambda} g_s(\lambda) = \frac{1}{\alpha} \text{Var}_{a \sim \pi_\lambda^*(\cdot|s)} (\log \pi_\beta(a|s)) \geq 0. \quad (20)$$

Consequently, the constraint $g(\lambda) := \mathbb{E}_{s \sim \mathcal{D}} [g_s(\lambda)]$ also satisfies $g'(\lambda) \geq 0$.

Proposition 4.1 shows the following intuition. As λ increases, the closed-form optimal policy π_λ^* assigns more probability mass to actions with larger π_β and yields a more conservative update. Conversely, a smaller λ allows π_λ^* to retain greater flexibility within the support of π_β and allows the update to be more strongly guided by advantage function. This monotonicity is consistent with the overall behavior of λ in the CCI framework, as shown in Tab. 1.

The detailed proof is provided in Appendix B.

Lemma 4.2 (Maximum Entropy Performance Difference). Let π and π_β be two stationary policies. Consider the maximum-entropy performance $\mathcal{J}(\pi) = \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim \pi} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t (r(s_t, a_t) - \alpha \log \pi(a_t|s_t)) \right]$, then the maximum entropy performance difference satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}(\pi) - \mathcal{J}(\pi_\beta) &= \\ &= \frac{1}{1 - \gamma} \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_\pi} \left[\mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} [\tilde{A}^{\pi_\beta}(s, a)] - \alpha \text{KL}(\pi(\cdot|s) \| \pi_\beta(\cdot|s)) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

where $\tilde{A}^{\pi_\beta}(s, a)$ is the advantage function under the shaped reward $\tilde{r}(s, a) = r(s, a) - \alpha \log \pi_\beta(a|s)$.

Theorem 4.3 (Performance Lower Bound for the Optimal Policy). Define $\epsilon_\beta(\pi) := \max_s \left| \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} [\tilde{A}^{\pi_\beta}(s, a)] \right|$, $\kappa_\beta(\pi) := \max_s \text{KL}(\pi(\cdot|s) \| \pi_\beta(\cdot|s))$ and the average total variation distance under ν by $\Delta_{\text{TV}}(\pi, \pi_\beta; \nu) := \mathbb{E}_{s \sim \nu} [D_{\text{TV}}(\pi(\cdot|s), \pi_\beta(\cdot|s))]$. Assume $|\log \pi_\beta(a|s)| \leq B$ for all (s, a) . For a given $\lambda \geq 0$ and $\alpha > 0$, π_λ^* satisfies the following maximum-entropy performance lower bound:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}(\pi_\lambda^*) &\geq \mathcal{J}(\pi_\beta) - \frac{2B|\lambda - \alpha|}{1 - \gamma} \Delta_{\text{TV}}(\pi_\lambda^*, \pi_\beta; d_{\pi_\beta}) \\ &\quad - \frac{4\alpha B + 2\gamma \left(\epsilon_\beta(\pi_\lambda^*) + \alpha \kappa_\beta(\pi_\lambda^*) \right)}{(1 - \gamma)^2} \Delta_{\text{TV}}(\pi_\lambda^*, \pi_\beta; d_{\pi_\beta}). \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Theorem 4.4 (Performance Lower Bound for a Parametric Policy). Define the suboptimality gap of a parametric policy π_θ by

$$\delta_\theta^{\text{sub}}(\lambda) := F_\lambda(\pi_\lambda^*) - F_\lambda(\pi_\theta) \geq 0, \quad (23)$$

where $F_\lambda(\pi) = \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_{\pi_\beta}} \left[\mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} \tilde{A}^{\pi_\beta}(s, a) - \alpha \text{KL}(\pi(\cdot|s) \parallel \pi_\beta(\cdot|s)) + (\lambda - \alpha) \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} \log \pi_\beta(a|s) \right]$.

Then π_θ satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}(\pi_\theta) \geq & \mathcal{J}(\pi_\beta) - \frac{2B|\lambda - \alpha|}{1 - \gamma} \Delta_{\text{TV}}(\pi_\theta, \pi_\beta; d_{\pi_\beta}) - \frac{\delta_\theta^{\text{sub}}(\lambda)}{1 - \gamma} \\ & - \frac{4\alpha B + 2\gamma(\epsilon_\beta(\pi_\theta) + \alpha\kappa_\beta(\pi_\theta))}{(1 - \gamma)^2} \Delta_{\text{TV}}(\pi_\theta, \pi_\beta; d_{\pi_\beta}). \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

The proofs of Theorems 4.3 and 4.4 suggest a decomposition of the lower bound into two components. The first-order term $\mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{1-\gamma}\right)$ evaluates policy improvement under the fixed state distribution d_{π_β} . The second-order term $\mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{(1-\gamma)^2}\right)$ captures distribution shift, arising from the mismatch between d_π and d_{π_β} .

Compared to the KL-density constraint in standard RL, whose performance lower bound is typically $\mathcal{J}^{\text{KL}}(\pi^*) \geq \mathcal{J}(\pi_\beta) - \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{(1-\gamma)^2}\right)$ (Lyu et al., 2022), our bound additionally exposes an explicit first-order term and makes the role of λ transparent: the factor $|\lambda - \alpha|$ quantifies how the λ modulates the worst-case performance.

The detailed proof is provided in Appendix C.

5. Experiments

5.1. Comparisons on D4RL Benchmarks

We evaluate ACPO on D4RL (Fu et al., 2021) and compare it with a diverse set of strong offline RL baselines.

Tasks. We conduct experiments in Gym-MuJoCo locomotion domains and more challenging AntMaze and Kitchen tasks. The main challenge of the latter is to learn policies for long-horizon planning from datasets that do not contain optimal trajectories, which require “stitching” ability.

Baselines. We select competitive offline RL baselines, including BCQ (Fujimoto et al., 2019), IQL (Kostrikov et al., 2021b), CQL (Kumar et al., 2020), TD3+BC (Fujimoto & Gu, 2021), SPOT (Wu et al., 2022), SWG (Tagle et al., 2025), EQL (Xu et al., 2023), DTQL (Chen et al., 2024).

Results. The whole results are shown in Tab. 2. Overall, ACPO demonstrates strong robustness across domains, achieving the best performance on Gym-MuJoCo and Kitchen tasks. On AntMaze, ACPO is slightly behind SWG and DTQL. A reason is that AntMaze requires trajectory-level planning and long-horizon credit assignment under sparse rewards, where diffusion-based methods (SWG/DTQL) are particularly effective. While these diffusion models achieve strong performance, their computational efficiency is also an important consideration.

5.2. Comparisons on NeoRL2 Benchmarks

We also evaluate ACPO on NeoRL2 benchmarks.

Tasks. NeoRL2 (Near Real-World Offline RL Benchmark) (Gao et al., 2025) is a recent benchmark designed to reflect practical constraints in offline RL. It includes domains motivated by industrial control, nuclear fusion, and healthcare, featuring pronounced time-delay effects and external disturbances. Moreover, practical data acquisition limits the dataset size and coverage, which places higher demands on the robustness and adaptiveness of offline RL algorithms.

Baselines. We compare against representative baselines commonly reported on NeoRL2, including BC, CQL (Kumar et al., 2020), EDAC (An et al., 2021), MCQ (Lyu et al., 2022), TD3+BC (Fujimoto & Gu, 2021), RAMBO (Rigter et al., 2022), and MOBILE (Sun et al., 2023)².

Results. As shown in Tab. 3, ACPO achieves clear improvements on NeoRL2. It attains the best performance on 4 out of 7 datasets and yields the highest total score across tasks, substantially outperforming the strongest baseline TD3+BC.

5.3. Special-Case Comparisons and λ Dynamics

Under the CCI framework, several representative policy constraints can be recovered by fixing the interpolation parameter λ . To isolate the effect of λ , we perform special-case comparisons by disabling the dual update in ACPO and training with a fixed λ throughout. These special cases match wBC, AWAC (Nair et al., 2020) and InAC (Xiao et al., 2023) at the level of the policy improvement. In contrast, the policy evaluation components may differ across methods; for a controlled comparison, we keep the policy evaluation fixed and use the same maximum-entropy critic updates Eq. (16) and (17) as ACPO in all variants.

Settings. For Gym-MuJoCo tasks, we set $\alpha = 0.1$. For NeoRL2 tasks, we set $\alpha = 0.5$. We instantiate three special cases by choosing: (i) practical wBC: $\lambda = 100$ to approximate the wBC regime, (ii) AWAC: $\lambda = \alpha$, and (iii) InAC: $\lambda = 0$.

Fig. 1 reports training curves of ACPO against these three baselines across six datasets, together with the adaptive evolution of λ during training. From Fig. 1, we draw the following observations:

Overall Superiority. ACPO consistently achieves the strongest performance across the six tasks, with particularly clear gains on the more challenging NeoRL2 datasets where coverage is limited. This highlights the benefit of automatically adapting the effective constraint regime to the dataset.

²We focus on the strongest baselines used in NeoRL2 and omit MOPO (Yu et al., 2020) and COMBO (Yu et al., 2021) for brevity.

Table 2. Averaged normalized scores on Gym-MuJoCo-v2, Antmaze-v2, and Kitchen-v0 datasets over five seeds. Scores are reported as mean \pm standard deviation. **Bold** indicates the best performance in each task.

Dataset	BCQ	IQL	CQL	TD3+BC	SPOT	SWG	EQL	DTQL	ACPO
halfcheetah-med	47.0	47.4	44.0	48.3	58.4	46.9	47.2	57.9	52.5 \pm 0.76
hopper-med	56.7	66.3	58.5	59.3	86.0	68.6	74.6	99.6	97.9 \pm 2.14
walker2d-med	72.6	78.3	72.5	83.7	86.4	74.0	87.0	89.4	88.0 \pm 1.1
halfcheetah-med-rep	40.4	44.2	45.5	44.6	52.2	42.5	44.5	50.9	47.5 \pm 0.54
hopper-med-rep	53.3	94.7	95.0	60.9	100.2	73.9	98.1	100.0	100.6 \pm 0.54
walker2d-med-rep	52.1	73.9	77.2	81.8	91.6	60.6	76.6	88.5	93.6 \pm 1.86
halfcheetah-med-exp	89.1	86.7	90.7	90.7	86.9	92.8	90.6	92.7	97.2 \pm 1.24
hopper-med-exp	81.8	91.5	105.4	98.0	99.3	109.9	105.5	109.3	112.3 \pm 0.72
walker2d-med-exp	109.0	109.6	109.6	110.1	112.0	110.7	110.2	110.0	113.1 \pm 0.22
Locomotion Total	602	692.6	698.4	677.4	773	679.9	734.3	798.3	802.7 \pm 9.12
antmaze-u	78.9	85.5	84.8	78.6	93.5	92.4	93.2	92.6	90.0 \pm 3.0
antmaze-u-d	55.0	66.7	43.4	71.4	40.7	70.0	65.4	74.4	86.0 \pm 3.4
antmaze-m-p	0	72.2	65.2	10.6	74.7	89.6	77.5	76.0	76.0 \pm 4.24
antmaze-m-d	0	71.0	54.0	3.0	79.1	88.2	70.0	80.6	76.0 \pm 4.24
antmaze-l-p	6.7	39.6	38.4	0.2	35.3	55.4	45.6	59.2	56.0 \pm 4.94
antmaze-l-d	2.2	47.5	31.6	0.0	36.3	55.2	42.5	62.0	48.0 \pm 4.98
Antmaze Total	142.8	382.5	317.4	163.8	359.6	450.8	394.2	444.8	432.0 \pm 24.8
kitchen-m	10.6	52.8	51.0	0.8	0.0	61.0	55.6	60.2	72.5 \pm 5.5
kitchen-p	18.9	46.1	49.8	0.0	0.0	69.0	74.5	74.4	64.0 \pm 15.52
Kitchen Total	29.5	98.9	100.8	0.8	0.0	130.0	130.1	134.6	136.5 \pm 21.02

Table 3. Averaged normalized scores on NeoRL2 benchmark over three seeds. Scores are reported as mean \pm standard deviation. **Bold** indicates the best performance in each task.

Dataset	Data	BC	CQL	EDAC	MCQ	TD3+BC	RAMBO	MOBILE	ACPO
Pipeline	69.3	68.6	81.1	72.9	49.7	82.0	24.1	65.5	95.2 \pm 4.62
Simglucose	73.9	75.1	11.0	8.1	29.6	74.2	10.8	9.3	94.9 \pm 12.73
RocketRecovery	75.3	72.8	74.3	65.7	76.5	79.7	-44.2	43.7	84.6 \pm 10.23
RandomFrictionHopper	28.7	28.0	33.0	34.7	31.7	29.5	29.6	35.1	33.7 \pm 0.37
DMSD	56.6	65.1	70.2	78.7	77.8	60.0	76.2	64.4	74.9 \pm 5.67
Fusion	48.8	55.2	55.9	58.0	49.7	54.6	59.6	5.0	61.8 \pm 2.07
SafetyHalfCheetah	73.6	70.2	71.2	53.1	54.7	68.6	-422.4	8.7	67.1 \pm 6.90
Total	426.2	435.0	396.7	371.2	369.7	448.6	-266.3	231.7	512.2 \pm 42.59

λ **Dynamics.** We observe that λ is often non-monotonic, typically rising in early training and gradually decaying afterwards. Early in training, critic estimates are less calibrated and actor updates are more prone to exploiting OOD actions. The dual update reacts by increasing λ , strengthening the constraint and biasing updates toward higher-density behavior actions to stabilize learning. As training progresses and value estimates become better calibrated, the OOD risk diminishes; λ decreases accordingly, relaxing the constraint and enabling more effective policy improvement.

5.4. Behavior Density Estimator Ablation Study

Since ACPO explicitly depends on $\log \pi_\beta(a|s)$, the choice of the behavior density estimator can directly affect both the constraint signal and the policy improvement weights.

Beyond a Gaussian density estimator for π_β , we additionally study the conditional variational auto-encoder (CVAE) model (Fujimoto et al., 2019; Han et al., 2025b) to approximate π_β . Moreover, motivated by prior work (Wu et al., 2022), we also adapt the IS corrected method to reduce estimation bias in expectations of π_β . We compare Gaussian vs. CVAE behavior models across 9 Gym-MuJoCo datasets, with results reported in Fig. 2.

As shown in Fig. 2, the Gaussian and CVAE behavior models yield comparable performance on most datasets, except for walker2d-medium-v2 and walker2d-medium-replay-v2, where the performance gap becomes pronounced. To diagnose this discrepancy, we visualize the distributions of $\log \pi_\beta(a|s)$ induced by the Gaussian and CVAE estimators on (i)

Figure 1. Special-case comparisons and the evolution of λ learned by ACPO during training.

Figure 2. Normalized score differences on Gym-MuJoCo datasets.

in-dataset actions a_{in} and (ii) perturbed OOD actions a_{ood} constructed as $a_{ood} = a_{in} + \xi z$, where ξ controls the perturbation scale and $z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)$. The resulting distributions are shown in Fig. 3,

Figure 3. Distributions of $\log \pi_{\beta}(a|s)$ under Gaussian and CVAE behavior estimators on in-dataset actions and OOD actions.

Fig. 3 explains the reason for weaker performance of

the CVAE estimator on walker2d-medium-v2 and walker2d-medium-replay-v2. On in-dataset actions, the CVAE induces a noticeably sharper $\log \pi_{\beta}(a|s)$ distribution than the Gaussian model, suggesting a more concentrated density estimate. More importantly, on perturbed OOD actions, the CVAE does not consistently assign sufficiently low likelihood compared with the Gaussian estimator: the distribution of $\log \pi_{\beta}(a_{ood}|s)$ is not shifted left as much as expected under clearly OOD perturbations. This overestimation of behavior likelihood for OOD actions can weaken the constraint signal in ACPO, increase susceptibility to extrapolation error, and ultimately degrade performance.

Training details for all experiments are provided in Appendix D.

6. Conclusion

We proposed CCI, a unified optimization framework that bridges weighted BC, KL-based density regularization, and support constraints as special cases along a common constraint spectrum. CCI exposes an explicit interpolation parameter that enables smooth transitions and principled combinations across constraint regimes. Building on CCI, we developed ACPO, a practical primal–dual algorithm that automatically adapts this constraint dial via a Lagrangian dual update. We further established a maximum-entropy performance difference lemma and derived performance lower bounds for both the closed-form optimal policy and its parametric projection. Experiments on D4RL and NeoRL2 show that ACPO achieves robust gains across diverse domains, often matching or exceeding strong baselines overall. As future work, extending ACPO to trajectory-level settings for long-horizon credit assignment and sparse rewards tasks is critical. Another promising direction is to incorporate dataset filtering to improve the reliability of behavior policy estimation.

7. Impact Statements

This paper presents work whose goal is to advance the field of machine learning. There are many potential societal consequences of our work, none of which we feel must be specifically highlighted here.

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A. Continuous Constraint Interpolation Framework

We start from the following constrained maximum-entropy policy optimization problem,

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\pi} \mathbb{E}_{s \sim \mathcal{D}, a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} [Q(s, a) - \alpha \log \pi(a|s)], \\ \text{s.t. } \mathbb{E}_{s \sim \mathcal{D}, a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} [\log \pi_{\beta}(a|s)] \geq \epsilon, \\ \int_a \pi(a|s) da = 1, \forall s. \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Solving the above constrained problem Eq. (25) via the Lagrangian,

$$\mathcal{L}(\pi, \lambda, \nu) = \mathbb{E}_{s \sim \mathcal{D}, a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} [Q(s, a) - \alpha \log \pi(a|s)] + \lambda [\mathbb{E}_{s \sim \mathcal{D}, a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} [\log \pi_{\beta}(a|s) - \epsilon]] + \mathbb{E}_{s \sim \mathcal{D}} \left[\nu(s) \left[\int_a \pi(a|s) da - 1 \right] \right], \quad (26)$$

To obtain the optimal non-parametric policy, we take the functional derivative of $\mathcal{L}(\pi, \lambda, \nu)$ w.r.t. $\pi(\cdot|s)$, and setting it to zero yields:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}(\pi, \lambda, \nu)}{\partial \pi} \\ &= Q(s, a) - \alpha(1 + \log \pi(a|s)) + \lambda \log \pi_{\beta}(a|s) + \nu(s), \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

Rearranging gives

$$\log \pi(a|s) = \frac{1}{\alpha} \left(Q(s, a) + \lambda \log \pi_{\beta}(a|s) + \nu(s) - \alpha \right). \quad (28)$$

Exponentiating both sides yields

$$\pi_{\lambda}^*(a|s) = \exp\left(\frac{\nu(s) - \alpha}{\alpha}\right) \exp\left(\frac{Q(s, a)}{\alpha}\right) \pi_{\beta}(a|s)^{\lambda/\alpha}. \quad (29)$$

Since the prefactor $\exp((\nu(s) - \alpha)/\alpha)$ does not depend on a , it can be absorbed into the normalizer, giving

$$\pi_{\lambda}^*(a|s) \propto \exp\left(\frac{Q(s, a)}{\alpha}\right) \pi_{\beta}(a|s)^{\lambda/\alpha}. \quad (30)$$

Enforcing $\int \pi_{\lambda}^*(a|s) da = 1$ yields the normalized closed-form solution

$$\pi_{\lambda}^*(a|s) = \exp\left(\frac{Q(s, a) - Z_{\lambda}(s)}{\alpha}\right) \pi_{\beta}(a|s)^{\lambda/\alpha}, \quad (31)$$

where $\lambda \geq 0$ and $\nu(s)$ are dual variables, and $Z_{\lambda}(s) = \alpha \log \int_a \exp\left(\frac{Q(s, a)}{\alpha}\right) \pi_{\beta}(a|s)^{\lambda/\alpha} da$.

Similarly within InAC (Xiao et al., 2023), we also replace $Z_{\lambda}(s)$ with value function $V(s)$. Therefore, the closed-form solution Eq. (31) can be transformed into the following form,

$$\pi_{\lambda}^*(a|s) \propto \exp\left(\frac{A(s, a)}{\alpha}\right) \pi_{\beta}(a|s)^{\lambda/\alpha}, \quad (32)$$

Then, we project the non-parametric optimal policy π_{λ}^* into the parametric space π_{θ} by minimizing the reverse KL divergence under the state distribution in dataset,

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{\theta}(a|s) &= \arg \min_{\pi_{\theta}} \mathbb{E}_{s \sim \mathcal{D}} [D_{\text{KL}}[\pi_{\lambda}^*(\cdot|s) || \pi_{\theta}(\cdot|s)]] \\ &= \arg \min_{\theta} \mathbb{E}_{s \sim \mathcal{D}} \left[\mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi_{\lambda}^*(\cdot|s)} [\log \pi_{\lambda}^*(a|s) - \log \pi_{\theta}(a|s)] \right] \\ &= \arg \min_{\theta} \mathbb{E}_{s \sim \mathcal{D}} \left[\mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi_{\beta}(\cdot|s)} \left[-\exp\left(\frac{A(s, a)}{\alpha}\right) \pi_{\beta}(a|s)^{(\lambda-\alpha)/\alpha} \log \pi_{\theta}(a|s) \right] \right] \\ &= \arg \max_{\theta} \mathbb{E}_{s \sim \mathcal{D}} \left[\mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi_{\beta}(\cdot|s)} \left[\exp\left(\frac{A(s, a)}{\alpha}\right) + \frac{\lambda - \alpha}{\alpha} \log \pi_{\beta}(a|s) \right] \log \pi_{\theta}(a|s) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

From Eq. (33), the policy improvement objective can be written in the dataset form

$$\max_{\theta} \mathcal{J}^{\text{CCI}}(\theta; \lambda) = \mathbb{E}_{(s,a) \sim \mathcal{D}} \left[w_{\lambda}(s, a) \log \pi_{\theta}(a|s) \right], \quad (34)$$

where $w_{\lambda}(s, a) = \exp \left(\frac{A(s,a)}{\alpha} + \frac{\lambda - \alpha}{\alpha} \log \pi_{\beta}(a|s) \right)$. This yields the CCI policy improvement objective Eq. (11).

Varying λ continuously interpolates the influence of the weight term $w_{\lambda}(s, a)$, yielding several representative regimes:

① **Support Constraint** $\lambda = 0$. When $\lambda = 0$, the objective becomes

$$\max_{\theta} \mathcal{J}^{\text{CCI}}(\theta; 0) = \mathbb{E}_{(s,a) \sim \mathcal{D}} \left[\exp \left(\frac{A(s,a)}{\alpha} - \log \pi_{\beta}(a|s) \right) \log \pi_{\theta}(a|s) \right], \quad (35)$$

which matches policy improvement objective used by InAC (Xiao et al., 2023).

② **Support-to-Density Constraint** $0 < \lambda < \alpha$. when $0 < \lambda < \alpha$, the objective becomes

$$\max_{\theta} \mathcal{J}^{\text{CCI}}(\theta; \alpha) = \mathbb{E}_{(s,a) \sim \mathcal{D}} \left[\exp \left(\frac{A(s,a)}{\alpha} + \frac{\alpha - \lambda}{\alpha} \log \pi_{\beta}(a|s) \right) \log \pi_{\theta}(a|s) \right], \quad (36)$$

As λ increases toward α , the update gradually shifts from support constraint toward KL-based density constraint.

③ **KL-based Density Constraint** $\lambda = \alpha$. When $\lambda = \alpha$, the objective becomes

$$\max_{\theta} \mathcal{J}^{\text{CCI}}(\theta; \alpha) = \mathbb{E}_{(s,a) \sim \mathcal{D}} \left[\exp \left(\frac{A(s,a)}{\alpha} \right) \log \pi_{\theta}(a|s) \right], \quad (37)$$

which matches the policy improvement objective in AWAC (Nair et al., 2020).

④ **Density-to-wBC Constraint** $\lambda > \alpha$. When $\lambda > \alpha$, the objective becomes

$$\max_{\theta} \mathcal{J}^{\text{CCI}}(\theta; \lambda) = \mathbb{E}_{(s,a) \sim \mathcal{D}} \left[\exp \left(\underbrace{\frac{A(s,a)}{\alpha}}_{\text{KL-density term}} + \underbrace{\frac{\lambda - \alpha}{\alpha} \log \pi_{\beta}(a|s)}_{\text{wBC term}} \right) \log \pi_{\theta}(a|s) \right]. \quad (38)$$

⑤ **Practical wBC** $\lambda \gg \alpha + A(s, a)(\log \pi_{\beta}(a|s))^{-1}$. When $\lambda \gg \alpha + A(s, a)(\log \pi_{\beta}(a|s))^{-1}$, then $\frac{\lambda - \alpha}{\alpha} \log \pi_{\beta}(a|s) \gg \frac{A(s,a)}{\alpha}$, the objective becomes

$$\max_{\theta} \mathcal{J}^{\text{CCI}}(\theta; \lambda) = \mathbb{E}_{(s,a) \sim \mathcal{D}} \left[\exp \left(\frac{\lambda - \alpha}{\alpha} \log \pi_{\beta}(a|s) \right) \log \pi_{\theta}(a|s) \right], \quad (39)$$

We note that the practical wBC regime corresponds to choosing $\lambda \gg \alpha + A(s, a)(\log \pi_{\beta}(a|s))^{-1}$. Next, we provide an explicit upper bound on $|A(s, a)(\log \pi_{\beta}(a|s))^{-1}|$ under the maximum-entropy setting.

In practice, we stabilize training by clipping log-probabilities for any stochastic policy: $\log \pi(a|s) \in [\ell_{\min}, \ell_{\max}]$. Define

$$C_{\max} \triangleq \max\{|\ell_{\min}|, |\ell_{\max}|\} \Rightarrow |-\alpha \log \pi(a|s)| \leq \alpha C_{\max},$$

In common RL reward setting, the reward function is bounded by $|r(s, a)| \leq R_{\max}$. Then the per-step soft reward satisfies $|r(s, a) - \alpha \log \pi(a|s)| \leq R_{\max} + \alpha C_{\max}$. By the discounted sum, we have $|Q^{\pi}(s, a)| \leq \frac{R_{\max} + \alpha C_{\max}}{1 - \gamma}$, $|V^{\pi}(s)| \leq \frac{R_{\max} + \alpha C_{\max}}{1 - \gamma}$. Therefore,

$$|A^{\pi}(s, a)| \leq |Q^{\pi}(s, a)| + |V^{\pi}(s)| \leq \frac{2(R_{\max} + \alpha C_{\max})}{1 - \gamma}. \quad (40)$$

It follows that

$$\left| \frac{A(s, a)}{\log \pi_{\beta}(a|s)} \right| \leq \frac{|A(s, a)|}{C_{\min}^{\beta} + \delta} \leq \frac{2(R_{\max} + \alpha C_{\max})}{(1 - \gamma)(C_{\min}^{\beta} + \delta)}. \quad (41)$$

Therefore, a sufficient condition for the practical wBC constraint is to choose $\lambda \gg \alpha + \frac{2(R_{\max} + \alpha C_{\max})}{(1-\gamma)(C_{\min}^{\beta} + \delta)}$, where $C_{\min}^{\beta} \triangleq \min |\log \pi_{\beta}(a|s)|$, and δ is a small constant introduced to avoid division by zero.

Summarizing the above, we can obtain Tab. 1.

In addition, SAC (Haarnoja et al., 2018) is another extreme initiation of the CCI framework, minimizing the forward KL divergence $D_{\text{KL}}[\pi_{\theta}(\cdot|s) \parallel \pi_{\lambda}^*(\cdot|s)]$, and setting $\lambda = 0$, then the policy improvement objective is

$$\max_{\theta} \mathcal{J}^{\text{SAC}}(\theta; 0) = \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi_{\theta}(\cdot|s)} \left[\exp\left(\frac{A(s, a)}{\alpha} - \log \pi_{\theta}(a|s)\right) \right], \quad (42)$$

which matches the policy improvement objective in SAC (Haarnoja et al., 2018).

B. Proof for Proposition 4.1

Proposition B.1. Fix any state s and temperature $\alpha > 0$. Let $\pi_{\lambda}^*(\cdot|s)$ denote the closed-form optimizer in Eq. (9) for a given $\lambda \geq 0$. Define

$$g_s(\lambda) := \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi_{\lambda}^*(\cdot|s)} [\log \pi_{\beta}(a|s)]. \quad (43)$$

Then $g_s(\lambda)$ is monotone non-decreasing in λ , and

$$\frac{d}{d\lambda} g_s(\lambda) = \frac{1}{\alpha} \text{Var}_{a \sim \pi_{\lambda}^*(\cdot|s)}(\log \pi_{\beta}(a|s)) \geq 0. \quad (44)$$

Consequently, $g(\lambda) := \mathbb{E}_{s \sim \mathcal{D}}[g_s(\lambda)]$ also satisfies $g'(\lambda) \geq 0$.

Proof. Fix s and abbreviate $Q(a) := Q(s, a)$ and $\pi_{\beta}(a) := \pi_{\beta}(a|s)$. Define the unnormalized density and the partition function

$$w_{\lambda}(a) := \exp\left(\frac{Q(a)}{\alpha}\right) \pi_{\beta}(a)^{\lambda/\alpha}, \quad \mathcal{Z}(\lambda) := \int w_{\lambda}(a) da, \quad (45)$$

so that $\pi_{\lambda}^*(a|s) = w_{\lambda}(a)/\mathcal{Z}(\lambda)$. By definition,

$$g_s(\lambda) = \int \pi_{\lambda}^*(a|s) \log \pi_{\beta}(a) da. \quad (46)$$

Differentiating Eq. (46) w.r.t. λ and exchanging derivative and integral,

$$\frac{d}{d\lambda} g_s(\lambda) = \int \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} \pi_{\lambda}^*(a|s) \log \pi_{\beta}(a) da. \quad (47)$$

Since $\pi_{\lambda}^* = w_{\lambda}/\mathcal{Z}(\lambda)$, we have

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} \pi_{\lambda}^*(a|s) = \frac{w'_{\lambda}(a)}{\mathcal{Z}(\lambda)} - \frac{w_{\lambda}(a)\mathcal{Z}'(\lambda)}{\mathcal{Z}(\lambda)^2} = \pi_{\lambda}^*(a|s) \left(\frac{w'_{\lambda}(a)}{w_{\lambda}(a)} - \frac{\mathcal{Z}'(\lambda)}{\mathcal{Z}(\lambda)} \right). \quad (48)$$

Using $w_{\lambda}(a) = \exp(Q(a)/\alpha) \exp((\lambda/\alpha) \log \pi_{\beta}(a))$, we obtain

$$\frac{w'_{\lambda}(a)}{w_{\lambda}(a)} = \frac{1}{\alpha} \log \pi_{\beta}(a). \quad (49)$$

Moreover,

$$\mathcal{Z}'(\lambda) = \int w'_{\lambda}(a) da = \int w_{\lambda}(a) \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha} \log \pi_{\beta}(a) da, \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{\mathcal{Z}'(\lambda)}{\mathcal{Z}(\lambda)} = \frac{1}{\alpha} \int \pi_{\lambda}^*(a|s) \log \pi_{\beta}(a) da = \frac{1}{\alpha} g_s(\lambda). \quad (50)$$

Substituting Eq. (49), (50) into Eq. (48) yields

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} \pi_{\lambda}^*(a|s) = \frac{1}{\alpha} \pi_{\lambda}^*(a|s) \left(\log \pi_{\beta}(a) - g_s(\lambda) \right). \quad (51)$$

Plugging Eq. (51) into Eq. (47) gives

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{d\lambda} g_s(\lambda) &= \frac{1}{\alpha} \int \pi_\lambda^*(a|s) \left(\log \pi_\beta(a) - g_s(\lambda) \right) \log \pi_\beta(a) da \\ &= \frac{1}{\alpha} \left(\mathbb{E}_{\pi_\lambda^*} [(\log \pi_\beta)^2] - \mathbb{E}_{\pi_\lambda^*} [\log \pi_\beta]^2 \right) = \frac{1}{\alpha} \text{Var}_{a \sim \pi_\lambda^*(\cdot|s)} (\log \pi_\beta(a)) \geq 0, \end{aligned}$$

which proves Eq. (44). The statement for $g(\lambda) = \mathbb{E}_{s \sim \mathcal{D}} [g_s(\lambda)]$ follows by linearity of expectation. \square

C. Proof for Performance Lower Bound

Lemma C.1 (Maximum-Entropy Performance Difference Lemma). *Let π and π_β be two stationary policies. Consider the maximum-entropy performance $\mathcal{J}(\pi) = \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim \pi} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t (r(s_t, a_t) - \alpha \log \pi(a_t|s_t)) \right]$. Then the maximum-entropy performance difference satisfies*

$$\mathcal{J}(\pi) - \mathcal{J}(\pi_\beta) = \frac{1}{1-\gamma} \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_\pi} \left[\mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} [\tilde{A}^{\pi_\beta}(s, a)] - \alpha D_{\text{KL}}(\pi(\cdot|s) \parallel \pi_\beta(\cdot|s)) \right], \quad (52)$$

where $\tilde{A}^{\pi_\beta}(s, a)$ is the advantage function under the shaped reward $\tilde{r}(s, a) = r(s, a) - \alpha \log \pi_\beta(a|s)$.

Proof. Introduce π_β into the entropy-regularized return:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}(\pi) &= \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim \pi} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t (r(s_t, a_t) - \alpha \log \pi(a_t|s_t)) \right] \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim \pi} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t (r(s_t, a_t) - \alpha \log \pi_\beta(a_t|s_t)) \right] - \alpha \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim \pi} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t \log \frac{\pi(a_t|s_t)}{\pi_\beta(a_t|s_t)} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (53)$$

Define the shaped return $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}(\pi) := \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim \pi} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t \tilde{r}(s_t, a_t) \right]$ with $\tilde{r}(s, a) = r(s, a) - \alpha \log \pi_\beta(a|s)$. Since $\log \frac{\pi_\beta(a|s)}{\pi_\beta(a|s)} = 0$, we have $\mathcal{J}(\pi_\beta) = \tilde{\mathcal{J}}(\pi_\beta)$ and thus

$$\mathcal{J}(\pi) - \mathcal{J}(\pi_\beta) = (\tilde{\mathcal{J}}(\pi) - \tilde{\mathcal{J}}(\pi_\beta)) - \alpha \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim \pi} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t \log \frac{\pi(a_t|s_t)}{\pi_\beta(a_t|s_t)} \right]. \quad (54)$$

For the first term, $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}$ is a standard discounted return with reward \tilde{r} . By the performance difference theorem (e.g., Lemma 6.1 in (Kakade & Langford, 2002)),

$$\tilde{\mathcal{J}}(\pi) - \tilde{\mathcal{J}}(\pi_\beta) = \frac{1}{1-\gamma} \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_\pi} \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} [\tilde{A}^{\pi_\beta}(s, a)]. \quad (55)$$

For the second term, using the discounted occupancy identity $d_\pi(s) = (1-\gamma) \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t \Pr(s_t = s | \pi)$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim \pi} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t \log \frac{\pi(a_t|s_t)}{\pi_\beta(a_t|s_t)} \right] &= \frac{1}{1-\gamma} \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_\pi} \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} \left[\log \frac{\pi(a|s)}{\pi_\beta(a|s)} \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{1-\gamma} \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_\pi} \left[D_{\text{KL}}(\pi(\cdot|s) \parallel \pi_\beta(\cdot|s)) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (56)$$

Substituting Eq. (55) and Eq. (56) into Eq. (54) yields Eq. (52). \square

Theorem C.2 (Performance Lower Bound for the Optimal Policy). *Define $\epsilon_\beta(\pi) := \max_s \left| \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} [\tilde{A}^{\pi_\beta}(s, a)] \right|$, $\kappa_\beta(\pi) := \max_s \text{KL}(\pi(\cdot|s) \parallel \pi_\beta(\cdot|s))$ and the average total variation distance under ν by $\Delta_{\text{TV}}(\pi, \pi_\beta; \nu) := \mathbb{E}_{s \sim \nu} [D_{\text{TV}}(\pi(\cdot|s), \pi_\beta(\cdot|s))]$. Assume $|\log \pi_\beta(a|s)| \leq B$ for all (s, a) . For a given $\lambda \geq 0$ and $\alpha > 0$, π_λ^* satisfies the following maximum-entropy performance lower bound:*

$$\mathcal{J}(\pi_\lambda^*) \geq \mathcal{J}(\pi_\beta) - \frac{2B|\lambda - \alpha|}{1-\gamma} \Delta_{\text{TV}}(\pi_\lambda^*, \pi_\beta; d_{\pi_\beta}) - \frac{4\alpha B + 2\gamma(\epsilon_\beta(\pi_\lambda^*) + \alpha \kappa_\beta(\pi_\lambda^*))}{(1-\gamma)^2} \Delta_{\text{TV}}(\pi_\lambda^*, \pi_\beta; d_{\pi_\beta}). \quad (57)$$

Proof. By the maximum-entropy performance difference lemma (Lemma C.1),

$$\mathcal{J}(\pi) - \mathcal{J}(\pi_\beta) = \frac{1}{1-\gamma} \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_\pi} \left[\mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} [\tilde{A}^{\pi_\beta}(s, a)] - \alpha D_{\text{KL}}(\pi(\cdot|s) \parallel \pi_\beta(\cdot|s)) \right]. \quad (58)$$

Let

$$f_\pi(s) := \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} [\tilde{A}^{\pi_\beta}(s, a)] - \alpha D_{\text{KL}}(\pi(\cdot|s) \parallel \pi_\beta(\cdot|s)),$$

so that the RHS of (58) equals $\frac{1}{1-\gamma} \mathbb{E}_{d_\pi} [f_\pi(s)]$. Decomposing around d_{π_β} yields

$$\mathbb{E}_{d_\pi} [f_\pi] = \mathbb{E}_{d_{\pi_\beta}} [f_\pi] + \left(\mathbb{E}_{d_\pi} [f_\pi] - \mathbb{E}_{d_{\pi_\beta}} [f_\pi] \right). \quad (59)$$

By definition of $\epsilon_\beta(\pi)$ and $\kappa_\beta(\pi)$, for all s we have

$$|f_\pi(s)| \leq \left| \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} [\tilde{A}^{\pi_\beta}(s, a)] \right| + \alpha D_{\text{KL}}(\pi(\cdot|s) \parallel \pi_\beta(\cdot|s)) \leq \epsilon_\beta(\pi) + \alpha \kappa_\beta(\pi),$$

hence

$$\left| \mathbb{E}_{d_\pi} [f_\pi] - \mathbb{E}_{d_{\pi_\beta}} [f_\pi] \right| \leq \|d_\pi - d_{\pi_\beta}\|_1 \left(\epsilon_\beta(\pi) + \alpha \kappa_\beta(\pi) \right). \quad (60)$$

Moreover, the divergence between discounted state visitation distributions (Lemma 3 in (Achiam et al., 2017)) gives

$$\|d_\pi - d_{\pi_\beta}\|_1 \leq \frac{2\gamma}{1-\gamma} \Delta_{\text{TV}}(\pi, \pi_\beta; d_{\pi_\beta}). \quad (61)$$

Combining (60) and (61) yields

$$\mathbb{E}_{d_\pi} [f_\pi] \geq \mathbb{E}_{d_{\pi_\beta}} [f_\pi] - \frac{2\gamma}{1-\gamma} \left(\epsilon_\beta(\pi) + \alpha \kappa_\beta(\pi) \right) \Delta_{\text{TV}}(\pi, \pi_\beta; d_{\pi_\beta}). \quad (62)$$

Substituting (62) into (58) and setting $\pi = \pi_\lambda^*$ yields

$$\mathcal{J}(\pi_\lambda^*) - \mathcal{J}(\pi_\beta) \geq \frac{1}{1-\gamma} \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_{\pi_\beta}} f_{\pi_\lambda^*}(s) - \frac{2\gamma}{(1-\gamma)^2} \left(\epsilon_\beta(\pi_\lambda^*) + \alpha \kappa_\beta(\pi_\lambda^*) \right) \Delta_{\text{TV}}(\pi_\lambda^*, \pi_\beta; d_{\pi_\beta}). \quad (63)$$

For the first term,

$$\mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_{\pi_\beta}} f_{\pi_\lambda^*}(s) = \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_{\pi_\beta}} \left[\mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi_\lambda^*(\cdot|s)} [\tilde{A}^{\pi_\beta}(s, a)] - \alpha D_{\text{KL}}(\pi_\lambda^*(\cdot|s) \parallel \pi_\beta(\cdot|s)) \right].$$

Next, define the auxiliary objective

$$F(\pi) := \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_{\pi_\beta}} \left[\mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} [A^{\pi_\beta}(s, a)] - \alpha D_{\text{KL}}(\pi(\cdot|s) \parallel \pi_\beta(\cdot|s)) + (\lambda - \alpha) \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} \log \pi_\beta(a|s) \right],$$

where $A^{\pi_\beta}(s, a)$ denotes the advantage under the original reward $r(s, a)$. Since π_λ^* maximizes F in the CCI optimization problem, we have $F(\pi_\lambda^*) \geq F(\pi_\beta)$. For π_β , note that $\mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi_\beta(\cdot|s)} [A^{\pi_\beta}(s, a)] = 0$ and $D_{\text{KL}}(\pi_\beta(\cdot|s) \parallel \pi_\beta(\cdot|s)) = 0$, hence

$$F(\pi_\beta) = (\lambda - \alpha) g_{d_{\pi_\beta}}(\pi_\beta), \quad g_{d_{\pi_\beta}}(\pi) := \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_{\pi_\beta}, a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} [\log \pi_\beta(a|s)].$$

Rearranging gives

$$\mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_{\pi_\beta}} \left[\mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi_\lambda^*(\cdot|s)} [A^{\pi_\beta}(s, a)] - \alpha D_{\text{KL}}(\pi_\lambda^*(\cdot|s) \parallel \pi_\beta(\cdot|s)) \right] \geq -(\lambda - \alpha) (g_{d_{\pi_\beta}}(\pi_\lambda^*) - g_{d_{\pi_\beta}}(\pi_\beta)). \quad (64)$$

We now relate \tilde{A}^{π_β} to A^{π_β} . Let $c(s, a) := -\alpha \log \pi_\beta(a|s)$ and $\tilde{r}(s, a) = r(s, a) + c(s, a)$. By linearity of value functions in reward,

$$\tilde{A}^{\pi_\beta}(s, a) = A^{\pi_\beta}(s, a) + A_c^{\pi_\beta}(s, a),$$

where $A_c^{\pi_\beta}$ is the advantage under the reward c alone. Since $|\log \pi_\beta(a|s)| \leq B$, we have $|c(s, a)| \leq \alpha B$, which implies $\|A_c^{\pi_\beta}\|_\infty \leq \frac{2\alpha B}{1-\gamma}$. Moreover, $\mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi_\beta(\cdot|s)}[A_c^{\pi_\beta}(s, a)] = 0$ for all s , hence for any π and s ,

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)}[A_c^{\pi_\beta}(s, a)] \right| &= \left| \int (\pi(a|s) - \pi_\beta(a|s)) A_c^{\pi_\beta}(s, a) da \right| \\ &\leq 2 \|A_c^{\pi_\beta}\|_\infty D_{\text{TV}}(\pi(\cdot|s), \pi_\beta(\cdot|s)) \\ &\leq \frac{4\alpha B}{1-\gamma} D_{\text{TV}}(\pi(\cdot|s), \pi_\beta(\cdot|s)). \end{aligned} \quad (65)$$

Therefore, for $\pi = \pi_\lambda^*$,

$$\mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_{\pi_\beta}} \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi_\lambda^*(\cdot|s)} \tilde{A}^{\pi_\beta}(s, a) \geq \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_{\pi_\beta}} \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi_\lambda^*(\cdot|s)} A^{\pi_\beta}(s, a) - \frac{4\alpha B}{1-\gamma} \Delta_{\text{TV}}(\pi_\lambda^*, \pi_\beta; d_{\pi_\beta}). \quad (66)$$

Combining (64) and (66) yields

$$\mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_{\pi_\beta}} f_{\pi_\lambda^*}(s) \geq -(\lambda - \alpha)(g_{d_{\pi_\beta}}(\pi_\lambda^*) - g_{d_{\pi_\beta}}(\pi_\beta)) - \frac{4\alpha B}{1-\gamma} \Delta_{\text{TV}}(\pi_\lambda^*, \pi_\beta; d_{\pi_\beta}). \quad (67)$$

Finally, for each state s , define

$$\Delta g_s := \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi_\lambda^*(\cdot|s)}[\log \pi_\beta(a|s)] - \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi_\beta(\cdot|s)}[\log \pi_\beta(a|s)].$$

Then

$$|\Delta g_s| \leq \int |\pi_\lambda^*(a|s) - \pi_\beta(a|s)| \cdot |\log \pi_\beta(a|s)| da \leq 2B D_{\text{TV}}(\pi_\lambda^*(\cdot|s), \pi_\beta(\cdot|s)), \quad (68)$$

and averaging over $s \sim d_{\pi_\beta}$ gives

$$|g_{d_{\pi_\beta}}(\pi_\lambda^*) - g_{d_{\pi_\beta}}(\pi_\beta)| \leq 2B \Delta_{\text{TV}}(\pi_\lambda^*, \pi_\beta; d_{\pi_\beta}). \quad (69)$$

Substituting (69) into (67) yields

$$\mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_{\pi_\beta}} f_{\pi_\lambda^*}(s) \geq -2B|\lambda - \alpha| \Delta_{\text{TV}}(\pi_\lambda^*, \pi_\beta; d_{\pi_\beta}) - \frac{4\alpha B}{1-\gamma} \Delta_{\text{TV}}(\pi_\lambda^*, \pi_\beta; d_{\pi_\beta}). \quad (70)$$

Plugging (70) into (63) completes the proof and yields Eq. (57). \square

Theorem C.3 (Performance Lower Bound for a Parametric Policy). *Define the suboptimality gap of a parametric policy π_θ by*

$$\delta_\theta^{\text{sub}}(\lambda) := F_\lambda(\pi_\lambda^*) - F_\lambda(\pi_\theta) \geq 0, \quad (71)$$

where $F_\lambda(\pi) = \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_{\pi_\beta}} \left[\mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} \tilde{A}^{\pi_\beta}(s, a) - \alpha D_{\text{KL}}(\pi(\cdot|s) \| \pi_\beta(\cdot|s)) + (\lambda - \alpha) \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} \log \pi_\beta(a|s) \right]$.

Then π_θ satisfies

$$\mathcal{J}(\pi_\theta) \geq \mathcal{J}(\pi_\beta) - \frac{2B|\lambda - \alpha|}{1-\gamma} \Delta_{\text{TV}}(\pi_\theta, \pi_\beta; d_{\pi_\beta}) - \frac{\delta_\theta^{\text{sub}}(\lambda)}{1-\gamma} - \frac{4\alpha B + 2\gamma(\epsilon_\beta(\pi_\theta) + \alpha\kappa_\beta(\pi_\theta))}{(1-\gamma)^2} \Delta_{\text{TV}}(\pi_\theta, \pi_\beta; d_{\pi_\beta}). \quad (72)$$

Proof. The derivation follows the same decomposition as in the proof of Theorem C.2. Applying Eq. (58) with $\pi = \pi_\theta$ and using the same occupancy-shift bound yields

$$\mathcal{J}(\pi_\theta) - \mathcal{J}(\pi_\beta) \geq \frac{1}{1-\gamma} \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_{\pi_\beta}} f_{\pi_\theta}(s) - \frac{2\gamma}{(1-\gamma)^2} (\epsilon_\beta(\pi_\theta) + \alpha\kappa_\beta(\pi_\theta)) \Delta_{\text{TV}}(\pi_\theta, \pi_\beta; d_{\pi_\beta}), \quad (73)$$

where

$$f_\pi(s) = \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)} [\tilde{A}^{\pi_\beta}(s, a)] - \alpha D_{\text{KL}}(\pi(\cdot|s) \| \pi_\beta(\cdot|s)).$$

We first lower bound the shaped-advantage term by the original advantage term, as in Eq. (66):

$$\mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_{\pi_\beta}, a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)}[\tilde{A}^{\pi_\beta}(s, a)] \geq \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_{\pi_\beta}, a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)}[A^{\pi_\beta}(s, a)] - \frac{4\alpha B}{1-\gamma} \Delta_{\text{TV}}(\pi, \pi_\beta; d_{\pi_\beta}). \quad (74)$$

Next, we convert the suboptimality gap in Eq. (71) into a baseline-anchored inequality. Since π_λ^* maximizes F_λ , we have $F_\lambda(\pi_\lambda^*) \geq F_\lambda(\pi_\beta)$. Combining this with Eq. (71) gives

$$F_\lambda(\pi_\theta) = F_\lambda(\pi_\lambda^*) - \delta_\theta^{\text{sub}}(\lambda) \geq F_\lambda(\pi_\beta) - \delta_\theta^{\text{sub}}(\lambda). \quad (75)$$

For π_β , $\mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi_\beta}[A^{\pi_\beta}(s, a)] = 0$ and $D_{\text{KL}}(\pi_\beta \| \pi_\beta) = 0$, hence $F_\lambda(\pi_\beta) = (\lambda - \alpha) g_{d_{\pi_\beta}}(\pi_\beta)$ where

$$g_{d_{\pi_\beta}}(\pi) := \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_{\pi_\beta}, a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)}[\log \pi_\beta(a|s)].$$

Rearranging Eq. (75) yields

$$\mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_{\pi_\beta}, a \sim \pi_\theta(\cdot|s)}[A^{\pi_\beta}(s, a)] - \alpha \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_{\pi_\beta}}[D_{\text{KL}}(\pi_\theta(\cdot|s) \| \pi_\beta(\cdot|s))] \geq -(\lambda - \alpha)(g_{d_{\pi_\beta}}(\pi_\theta) - g_{d_{\pi_\beta}}(\pi_\beta)) - \delta_\theta^{\text{sub}}(\lambda). \quad (76)$$

Finally, we bound the density-shaping difference by total variation. For each state s , define

$$\Delta g_s := \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi_\theta(\cdot|s)}[\log \pi_\beta(a|s)] - \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi_\beta(\cdot|s)}[\log \pi_\beta(a|s)].$$

Then

$$|\Delta g_s| \leq 2B D_{\text{TV}}(\pi_\theta(\cdot|s), \pi_\beta(\cdot|s)), \quad (77)$$

and averaging over $s \sim d_{\pi_\beta}$ yields

$$|g_{d_{\pi_\beta}}(\pi_\theta) - g_{d_{\pi_\beta}}(\pi_\beta)| \leq 2B \Delta_{\text{TV}}(\pi_\theta, \pi_\beta; d_{\pi_\beta}). \quad (78)$$

Combining Eq. (74), Eq. (76), and Eq. (78) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_{\pi_\beta}} f_{\pi_\theta}(s) &= \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_{\pi_\beta}} \left[\mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi_\theta(\cdot|s)} \tilde{A}^{\pi_\beta}(s, a) - \alpha D_{\text{KL}}(\pi_\theta(\cdot|s) \| \pi_\beta(\cdot|s)) \right] \\ &\geq -2B|\lambda - \alpha| \Delta_{\text{TV}}(\pi_\theta, \pi_\beta; d_{\pi_\beta}) - \frac{4\alpha B}{1-\gamma} \Delta_{\text{TV}}(\pi_\theta, \pi_\beta; d_{\pi_\beta}) - \delta_\theta^{\text{sub}}(\lambda). \end{aligned} \quad (79)$$

Plugging Eq. (79) into Eq. (73) completes the proof and yields Eq. (72). \square

D. Experimental Details

D.1. Implementation Details for D4RL Experiments

The vast majority of hyperparameters used in our D4RL experiments are summarized in Tab. 4.

The dataset abbreviations used in Tab. 2 and their corresponding full names are listed in Tab. 5.

Training curves for all D4RL tasks are provided in Fig. 5.

D.2. Implementation Details for NeoRL2 Experiments

The vast majority of hyperparameters used in our NeoRL2 experiments are summarized in Tab. 6.

Training curves for all NeoRL2 tasks are provided in Fig. 6.

D.3. Additional Details for Special-Case Comparisons and λ Dynamics

In Section 5.3, we keep all hyperparameters consistent with Tab. 4 and Tab. 6. We additionally specify the key settings in the main text: “For Gym-MuJoCo tasks, we set $\alpha = 0.1$. For NeoRL2 tasks, we set $\alpha = 0.5$. We instantiate three special cases by choosing: (i) practical wBC: $\lambda = 100$ to approximate the wBC regime, (ii) AWAC: $\lambda = \alpha$, and (iii) InAC: $\lambda = 0$.”

Table 4. D4RL hyperparameters, where s_{dim} and a_{dim} are the state and action dimensions, respectively.

Hyperparameter	Value	Task
Actor architecture	$s_{\text{dim}} - 256 - 256 - 2a_{\text{dim}}$	All
Q -network	$(s_{\text{dim}} + a_{\text{dim}}) - 256 - 256 - 1$	All
Value network	$s_{\text{dim}} - 256 - 256 - 1$	All
Behavior network	$s_{\text{dim}} - 512 - 512 - 2a_{\text{dim}}$	All
Activation	ReLU	All
Learning rate (actor & critic)	$5e - 4 \rightarrow 1e - 4$ (CosineAnnealingLR)	All
Learning rate (behavior policy)	$1e - 4$	All
Learning rate (λ)	$1e - 5$	All
Target Q soft update rate τ	$5e - 3$	All
Evaluation epochs	10	Gym-MuJoCo & Kitchen
	50	AntMaze
Evaluation frequency	$5e3$	All
Batch size	256	All
Discount factor γ	0.99	All
Temperature α	0.1	All
Initial λ	0.1 ($\lambda = \alpha$)	All
	-5.0	Hopper
	-0.2	HalfCheetah & AntMaze
ϵ in Eq. (7)	-0.7	Walker2d
	-1.0	Kitchen

Table 5. Dataset abbreviations for D4RL.

Dataset abbreviation	Dataset full name
halfcheetah-med	halfcheetah-medium-v2
hopper-med	hopper-medium-v2
walker2d-med	walker2d-medium-v2
halfcheetah-med-rep	halfcheetah-medium-replay-v2
hopper-med-rep	hopper-medium-replay-v2
walker2d-med-rep	walker2d-medium-replay-v2
halfcheetah-med-exp	halfcheetah-medium-expert-v2
hopper-med-exp	hopper-medium-expert-v2
walker2d-med-exp	walker2d-medium-expert-v2
antmaze-u	antmaze-umaze-v2
antmaze-u-d	antmaze-umaze-diverse-v2
antmaze-m-p	antmaze-medium-play-v2
antmaze-m-d	antmaze-medium-diverse-v2
antmaze-l-p	antmaze-large-play-v2
antmaze-l-d	antmaze-large-diverse-v2
kitchen-m	kitchen-mixed-v0
kitchen-p	kitchen-partial-v0

D.4. Additional Details for Behavior Density Estimator Ablation

In the experiments of Subsection 5.4, we run inference with the trained Gaussian and CVAE behavior models on the full datasets of `walker2d-medium-v2` and `walker2d-medium-replay-v2`, producing the distribution curves shown in Fig. 3. In addition to $\xi = 0.3$, we also evaluate $\xi \in \{0.1, 0.5, 0.8\}$, with the corresponding curves reported in Fig. 4. The conclusions remain unchanged: compared with the Gaussian estimator, the CVAE likelihood on perturbed OOD actions is not consistently suppressed.

Table 6. NeoRL2 hyperparameters. Architectures are denoted by MLP layer sizes, where s_{dim} and a_{dim} are the state and action dimensions, respectively.

Hyperparameter	Value	Task
Actor architecture	$s_{\text{dim}} - 256 - 256 - 2a_{\text{dim}}$	All
Q -network	$(s_{\text{dim}} + a_{\text{dim}}) - 256 - 256 - 1$	All
Value network	$s_{\text{dim}} - 256 - 256 - 1$	All
Behavior network	$s_{\text{dim}} - 512 - 512 - 2a_{\text{dim}}$	All
Activation	ReLU	All
Learning rate (actor & critic)	$5e - 4 \rightarrow 1e - 4$ (CosineAnnealingLR)	All
Learning rate (behavior policy)	$1e - 4$	All
Learning rate (λ)	$1e - 5$	All
Target Q soft update rate τ	$5e - 3$	All
Evaluation epochs	10	All
Evaluation frequency	$5e3$	All
Batch size	256	All
Discount factor γ	0.99	All
Temperature α	0.5	All
Initial λ	$0.5 (\lambda = \alpha)$	All
ϵ in Eq. (7)	-5.0	Simglucose & Pipeline
	-10.0	SafetyHalfCheetah & RocketRecovery & Fusion
	-2.0	RandomFrictionHopper
	-0.5	DMSD

 Figure 4. Gaussian and CVAE behavior models under $\xi \in \{0.1, 0.5, 0.8\}$.

Figure 5. D4RL Learning Curves.

Figure 6. NeoRL2 Learning Curves.